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**TRIPTYCH “DEDICATION TO AGDAM”
IN THE WORKS OF ARIF HUSEYNOV
(IN THE CONTEXT OF ICONOGRAPHIC ANALYSIS)**

Abstract. Azerbaijani art reflects the processes occurring at all stages of history. On September 27, 2020, the Azerbaijani army fought to protect its territorial integrity as a result of Armenia’s violation of the ceasefire again. The Azerbaijani army, who showed heroism for 44 days, won victory by raising our tricolor flag in our cultural capital Shusha on November 8. Agdam, which was occupied by the Armenian army on July 23, 1993, was returned without a war according to the agreement signed between Azerbaijan, Russia and Armenia on November 20, 2020. The theme of Victory is a leitmotif in the works of outstanding artists of Azerbaijani fine art. In this article, the triptych “Dedication to Agdam” created by Arif Huseynov is analyzed in the context of art criticism.

Key words: Azerbaijan, victory, Karabakh, Agdam, Arif Huseynov.

Introduction. Azerbaijani art reflects the processes occurring at all stages of history. The Karabakh tragedy that befell our people in the 90s was lived in our art for 30 years. On September 27, 2020, the Azerbaijani army fought to protect its territorial integrity as a result of Armenia’s violation of the ceasefire again. The Azerbaijani army, who showed heroism for 44 days, won victory by raising our tricolor flag in our cultural capital Shusha on November 8. The historical success achieved was the realization of a long-awaited dream of artists working in the field of art. The theme of Victory is a leitmotif in the works of outstanding artists of Azerbaijani

fine art. The image they create in the compositions is emphasized through more effective colors, lines, and plasticity. People's artist Arif Huseynov is one of the artists who is always distinguished by his patriotic stance. In his work, the series "Garabagname", "Prominent artists of Shusha" occupy an important position in terms of presenting historical and aesthetic views in a complete form.

The interpretation of the main material. Agdam, which was occupied by the Armenian army on July 23, 1993, was returned without a war according to the agreement signed between Azerbaijan, Russia and Armenia on November 10, 2020. [3]. The city of Agdam was destroyed within 30 years and lost its greatness. In the works of Arif Huseynov, we can see the image of the city called "Hiroshima of the Caucasus" with an impressive color gamut.

The "Dedication to Agdam" triptych was presented in front of the remains of the destroyed Drama Theater of the city, which was liberated from occupation in 2021. The main idea is the struggle between good and evil forces, the disasters that befell our historical land evoke a sense of sadness in every citizen of Azerbaijan. Each part of the triptych is history. The sequence of the artist's position exposes the inhuman face of Armenia, which tries to erase our cultural and historical heritage. People's artist based on historical facts in triptych, executed in 2021 on canvas, acrylic technique.

In the right part of the triptych, the symbolic Shahbulag fortress of Agdam was depicted. According to historians, Panahali Khan, the founder of the Karabakh Khanate, built a castle complex, stone and lime mosques, houses, and a bazaar near the spring known as "Shahbulag" 10 kilometers from the city of Aghdam. The castle got its name from the name of the gurgling spring. The monument, better known as Shahbulag in scientific literature, was the interior of a large palace complex. Shahbulag Castle is one of the simple examples of the military architecture of the Azerbaijani Khanate period. Shahbulag buildings had an impact on the architecture of the Karabakh Khanate, especially the city of Shusha, which was its capital. The fairy-tale characteristic of the artist's work brings a new breath to the work. The image of Panahali Khan and his warriors on the moon is the image of the freedom of their souls [4].

**Fig. 1. A. Huseynov. “Dedication to Agdam” triptych.
“Shahbulag Castle” (2021) (canvas, acrylic, 60x90 cm).**

In the central part, the destruction of the Agdam theater, characters playing “Leyli and Majnun”, “Othello” and “Don Quixote” are killed by evil forces on the stage. Black forces destroyed the famous drama theater after occupying Agdam, Armenia. A ruined theater was presented in the background.

Fig. 2. A. Huseynov. “Dedication to Agdam” triptych. “Destruction of Agdam Theater” (2021) (canvas, acrylic, 120x90 cm).

The depiction of Agdam Juma Mosque in the triptych is the preservation and restoration of Islamic religious traditions in the liberated city. When it became an important trade center in the region, one of the examples of the 19th century religious architecture of Karabakh was built in the city. In 1868-1870, this monument, which is a Juma mosque in Aghdam, was erected by the architect Karbalayi Safikhan Karabagi, the leading artist of Karabakh architecture. The architect continued the tradition of Juma mosques with double minarets, widespread in medieval Azerbaijani architecture, and created the image of a mosque in Agdam mosque in accordance with the requirements of his time and the architectural and construction experience of Karabakh. Arif Huseynov’s composition presented the image of the martyrs who saved the destroyed mosque with their own hands to the sound of the call to prayer.

Fig. 3. A. Huseynov. “Dedication to Agdam” triptych. “Agdam. Juma Mosque” (2021) (canvas, acrylic, 60x90 cm).

Conclusion. The main results of the article “Dedication to Agdam” triptych (in the context of iconographic analysis) by Arif Huseynov are as follows:

- “Dedication to Agdam” triptych was analyzed in the context of art studies.

– In the analysis of the work, the historicity of the iconographic analysis method and the image principles of fine art were used.

“Dedication to Agdam” triptych occupies an important place in modern Azerbaijani fine art.

After the liberation of Karabakh from occupation, it will be reconstructed and become an example for the countries of the world...

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Emil Ağayev (Azərbaycan)

ARIF HÜSEYNOV YARADICILIĞINDA “AĞDAMA İTHAF” TRİPTİXİ (İKONOQRAFİK TƏHLİL KONTEKSTİNDƏ)

Azərbaycan incəsənəti tarixin bütün mərhələlərində baş verən prosesləri özündə əks etdirir. 2020-ci il 27 sentyabr tarixində Azərbaycan ordusu ermənistanın növbəti dəfə atəşkəsi pozması nəticəsində öz ərazi bütövlüyünü qorumaq üçün mübarizəyə qalxdı. 44 gün ərzində qəhrəmanlıq göstərən Azərbaycan ordusu 8 noyabrda mədəniyyət paytaxtımız Şuşada üçrəngli bayrağımızı ucaldaraq Zəfər qazandı. 23 iyul 1993-cü ildə ermənistandan ordusu tərəfindən işğal edilən Ağdam, 2020-ci il 20 noyabr tarixində Azərbaycan, Rusiya və ermənistandan arasında bağlanan müqaviləyə əsasən müharibəsiz geri qaytarılır. Azərbaycan təsviri sənətinin görkəmli rəssamlarının yaradıcılığında Zəfər mövzusu leytmotiv təşkil edir. Bu məqalədə Arif Hüseynov yaradıcılığında “Ağdama ithaf” triptixi sənətşünaslıq kontekstində təhlil edilmişdir.

Açar sözlər: Azərbaycan, Zəfər, Qarabağ, Ağdam, Arif Hüseynov.

Эмиль Агаев (Азербайджан)

**ТРИПТИХ “ПОСВЯЩЕНИЕ АГДАМУ” АРИФА ГУСЕЙНОВА
(В КОНТЕКСТЕ ИКОНОГРАФИЧЕСКОГО АНАЛИЗА)**

Азербайджанское искусство отражает процессы, происходящие на всех этапах истории. 27 сентября 2020 года азербайджанская армия вступила в бои по защите своей территориальной целостности в результате очередного нарушения Арменией режима прекращения огня. Азербайджанская армия, проявлявшая героизм в течение 44 дней, одержала победу, подняв 8 ноября в культурной столице страны Шуше наш трехцветный флаг. Агдам, оккупированный армянской армией 23 июля 1993 года, был возвращен без войны согласно договору, подписанному между Азербайджаном, Россией и Арменией 10 ноября 2020 года. Тема Победы является лейтмотивом в творчестве выдающихся художников азербайджанского изобразительного искусства. В данной статье триптих Арифа Гусейнова «Посвящение Агдаму» анализируется в контексте иконографических проблем.

Ключевые слова: Азербайджан, Победа, Карабах, Агдам, Ариф Гусейнов.